

The Atlantic
Testing Platform for
Maritime Robotics

Topic	ICT-09-2019-2020 (H2020)
Acronym	ATLANTIS
Title	The Atlantic Testing Platform for Maritime Robotics: New Frontiers for Inspection and Maintenance of Offshore Energy Infrastructures.
Project number	871571
Delivery date	30.06.2021
Deliverable number	D7.5
Dissemination level	Confidential
Lead Beneficiary	RINA-C

First Exploitation strategy report

RINA-C

